

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

www.soildiveragro.eu
 @SoildiverAgro
 info@soildiveragro.eu

Universidade de Vigo

- auringonvalosta iloa ja hyötyä

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

WHAT IS SOILDIVERAGRO?

SoildiverAgro is a project funded by the European Horizon 2020 programme aimed at the adoption of new management practices and cropping systems that enhance soil genetic and functional biodiversity to reduce the use of external inputs while increasing crop production and quality, the delivery of ecosystem services and the EU agricultural stability and resilience.

We will create new knowledge about the beneficial effects of genetic and functional soil biodiversity (micro and macro organisms) on crop production, contributing to the establishment of soil biodiversity targets and proposes for integrating soil biodiversity into farming practices.

WHAT IS OUR IMPACT?

WHAT WE DO?

SoildiverAgro is organized around 6 geographical areas where 15 case studies will be performed to better understand how soil organism's benefits can be applied to improve resource uptake, plant growth development and health.

The case studies are organized around 3 different crops (potatoes, wheat and vegetables) in mono and diversified cropping systems.

MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH

Stakeholders identification

Stakeholder's engagement

BOREAL		
15 LUKE	POTATOE	Nutrient catch crops
14 LUKE	WHEAT	Till systems
13 LUKE	POTATOE	By-products
NEMORAL		
12 ESTI	POTATOE CEREAL CROPS	Till system Pest alert systems Suitable crop diversification
CONTINENTAL		
11 THÜNEN	WHEAT	Organisms interaction management
10 THÜNEN	POTATOE	
ATLANTIC CENTRAL		
9 ILVO	WHEAT	By-products
8 ILVO	LEEK CABBAGE	Till systems By-products
7 ILVO	POTATOE	Suitable crop diversification
6 ILVO	POTATOE	By-products Suitable crop diversification
LUSITANEAN		
5 UVIGO	POTATOE WHEAT	Pest alert system
4 UVIGO	POTATOE	Mycorrhiza
3 UVIGO	POTATOE	Suitable crop diversification Trap crops for pest control
MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH		
2 UPCT	WHEAT	By-products
1 UPCT	POTATOE	Suitable crop diversification Plant growth promoting bacteria

